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Date of submission for revision - 06.12.2022

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Date of revision and grading :

Paper grade : 5 / 5,5

«What factors led to the outbreak of the First World War?»

The First World War was one of the bloodiest global conflicts in history that caused estimatey 20 million deaths (*According to Nadège Mougel, 2011*). The war led to tectonic changes in world order, political, economic and social life. Only 1 empire, that took part in the First World War survived it, while German, Russian, Ottoman and Austro-Hungarian empires perished. On the other hand, and part of the world raised new force and center of power - the United States of America, the only one nation except Japan, which succeed in increasing of national wealth in the years of WW1. Awareness of the causes of the First World War are as important as understanding the conflict's devastating effect. It is believed that the cause of the First World War was the assassination of Archduke Franz Ferdinand, but the assassination was only the immediate cause, the «push» to war, while numerous hidden factors gradually led to it, the main of which was the desire of the German Empire to dominate the world and the competing national interests of the largest European powers.

The growth of the political crisis in the world, the aggravation of contradictions at the end of the 19th century and especially at the beginning of the 20th century led

to the creation of two hostile military-political alliances in Europe: The Entente, which united Britain, France and Russia, and the «Triple Alliance», which included Germany, Austria-Hungary, and Italy. The main cause of the conflict was an unprecedented escalation of disputes between the world's leading countries due to the unevenness of their economic development, the balance of power in the world economic system changed. German population raised from 48 million of people in 1888 to 66 million of people in 1913 making German Empire the most populated country in Europe, steel production in Germany raised by 1300% from 1886 to 1910 making Germany largest steel producer in Europe, German total import-export trade increased by 220% making it second largest trader in Europe after Britain, German shipping flow increased from 700 ships in 1885 to 2000 ships in 1911. (*According to Arthur P. Maloney 1984*). Last two factors were the most threatening to France and especially to the British empire.

Before the outbreak of WW1 Britain and France were the most powerful colonial forces, at the same time the German empire in parallel with its rapid development planned not only economic, but also colonial expansion, primarily on the African continent. In this situation, the British Empire could not stand idle against the backdrop of the growing ambitions of Germany and its support for the Boers during the Second Boer War in 1899-1902. German plans to create the Berlin-Baghdad railway with endpoints at the ports of the Persian Gulf and Gulf of Aden led to an additional escalation, nullified the trade sea route controlled by the British side that ran through the Suez Canal and the Mediterranean Sea, gave Germany the opportunity to freely intensify trade and economic cooperation with

its colonies in Africa and the entire Asia-Pacific region, bypassing the British Empire. From this point of view, the further development of the road and the launch of freight traffic along it at full capacity did not suit the British elite, who lost not only cash receipts from the transportation of German goods, but also control over German trade relations. The construction of the Berlin-Baghdad line indirectly led to an increase in military tension in Europe and became one of the factors that led Europe to the First World War. These factors with German-British trade and economic contradictions led to the abandonment of the British «Splendid isolation» policy after signing allied agreements with Japan in 1902 and with France in 1904 - the Entente.

It will be fair to say that colonial contradictions were much more critical in German-French relations, especially in Africa. After the Tangier crisis German-France relationship worsened to a critical level because of the unsuccessful result of Algeciras conference both for Germany, who were subjected to diplomatic isolation, with an exception for Austro-Hungary, and France, whose protectorate initiative in Morocco was delayed. In 5 years, because of mutual German-France dissatisfaction, the Agadir crisis flared with new force on Moroccan territory. After the uprising began in Morocco in 1911 French forces occupied Fess arguing this with the need to «restore order and protect French citizens», Germany turned to the «Gunboat diplomacy» responding with its fleet entering Agadir. Berlin did not dispute with French plan of establishing a protectorate in Morocco, at the same time Britain were pushing France to more resolute actions, while Germany began to for territorial «compensation» from

France. Eventually, after British statements about the inadmissibility of resolving the Agadir issue without the participation of Britain, since otherwise Britain would not be inactive, which meant the threat of war, the Germans and French sat down at the negotiating table. In November 1911, the parties came to an agreement that turned out to be even more unfavorable for Germany, which instead of the desired Morocco received the swamps and tropical forests of the French Congo. Subsequently, this led to the growth of chauvinist sentiment in Germany, where imperialist ambitions reached a level never seen before. In the same atmosphere of chauvinism, the candidacy of Poincare was put forward in France, who at the beginning of 1912 became prime minister and then president of the republic. The main goal of the new president was to prepare for war against Germany in order to return Alsace and Lorraine. The Agadir crisis had the same effect on England, where anti-German agitation intensified.

An equally important consequence of the «Panther's jump» - the entry of a German gunboat into Morocco, was the aggravation of the Dreadnought Race and the Arms Race in Europe as a whole. Charles L. Glaser claims: *«Arms races take center stage in the international relations during crises. Country has three fundamental options for acquiring the military weapons it needs to accomplish its foreign objectives: gaining allies, partnering with its enemy to lessen threats, and increasing its arsenal»*. Both Entente and Central powers choose arsenal expending their arsenals, which only exacerbated the international crisis and its subsequent escalation. The more one country armed itself, the more the other prepared for war. As a result, tensions rose to a boiling point in the region that would later become

known as Europe's "powder keg" - the Balkans. The Bosnian crisis of 1908 was not just a catalyst, but a direct precondition for the Sarajevo assassination and, subsequently, the war.

After annexation of Bosnia, Austro-Hungary began a new round of tension in the Balkans began a new round of tension in the Balkans and worsening relations with Serbia and Russia as much as possible, since these countries considered the annexation a direct violation of the Berlin Treaty. Since Bosnia was mainly inhabited by Slavs, for Serbia, as well as for Russia, this gave rise to the realization of its pan-Slavic ambitions, which significantly influenced the incitement of nationalist anti-Austrian sentiment in the region. The non-recognition of annexation by Serbia, according to the Russian government, would lead to an attack by Austria-Hungary, which would force Russia to enter the war, including against Germany, for which the Russians were not ready after the background of the defeat in the Russo-Japanese War. As a result, under pressure from its main ally, Serbia recognized, but did not accept the annexation, continuing to build up its military potential, becoming an increasing threat, according to Austria. Russia suffered a severe diplomatic defeat with rehearsal consequences, and the crisis itself was a manifestation of strategic frivolity with the consequences of creating long-term foreign policy risks that resulted in the outbreak of the First World War. However, the Balkans were not the only boiling point in Russo-Austrian relations. According to Guido Hausmann: «*The region of Ukrainian settlement became one of the central theatres of war on the eastern front*», Russia used to control 80% of Ukraine and wanted to seize its western part in order to realize its imperial

ambitions, which it called "the ideas of pan-Slavism", at the same time, Austria sought not only to maintain control over Western Ukraine, but also to expand its possessions in Volyn and Podolia. Moreover, Germany planned not only to expand its possessions at the expense of Ukrainian territories in the east and south, but also believed that the occupation of Ukraine was a necessary step to defeat Russia. Such interest in Ukraine is caused not only by the fact that it is located in the center of Europe between East and West, but also by its economic characteristics: In the 19th century Ukraine was Russia's main granary. The Donbas turned into the main mining and metallurgical center of Ukraine, and Odesa became its main seaport - Ukraine was producing 78 percent of the Empire's coal, 75 percent of iron ore, 56 percent of steel, the proceeds from the export of Ukraine-produced sugar, food, and fodder grains filled the imperial treasury : from 1893 to 1910, Russia received almost 3.3 billion rubles from Ukraine while spending 2.6 billion rubles on Ukraine's needs, the difference went to funding the imperial army and developing other parts of Russia (*According to Nazar Gorin, 2022*). Ultimately, one's of the largest battles of the First World War took place in Ukraine - the Brusilovsky Offensive and the Battle of Galicia, which in total, according to Alex Brown's estimates, were the result of 2,972,000 human casualties.

To summarize, in addition with dramatic human losses, the First World War led to colossal changes in all aspects of human life, many of these consequences still have an impact on the modern world order. Apart from the obvious reasons such as the Arms Race or the Sarajevo Murder, the Great War was preceded by a number of factors and events that increased tension between the 2 blocks and each of these

crises could potentially escalate into a full-scale war, which subsequently happened. The impossibility of constructive dialogue and non-realizing the potential consequences of a major war due to the certainty that the conflict would end quickly between the centers of power in Europe led to a constant “higher stake” and resulted in a global war in which the assassination of the Archduke was used only as an excuse to start hostilities. To be sure, the rise of the German Empire and its ambitions was a pretext for fueling chauvinist and imperialist sentiments in the rest of Europe, although equally anti-German sentiment was used as a casus belli by the Entente countries to further their own strategic plans. Summing up, we can say with confidence that the First World War was the logical result of the imbalance of power in Europe and, so to speak, the mutual desire of both sides of the conflict to resolve the existing contradictions by force.

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